

Reaction of rice varieties to brown planthopper (BPH) attack at Aduthurai, India.

Cultivar	Source	BPH population (mean no./ seedling)
ARC6564	AICRIP MR5	2.5
ARC6519	AICRIP MR6	3.0
ARC14636	AICRIP BPHS88	3.0
ARC14166-A	AICRIP MR16	2.8
T1426	AICRIP MR3	3.1
Manohar Sali	AICRIP BPHS122	2.9
Parakulaw	AICRIP MR4	2.8
IET6187	AICRIP BPHRVT (Kh '78)	2.7
PTB33	IRRI-IRTP No. 03302	2.0
Hondarawala (Acc. 15634)	IRRI-IRTP No. 04861	2.0
PTB19 (Athikraya) (Acc. 61 07)	IRRI-IRTP No. 01151	1.9
TN1 (susceptible check)		21.4
Java (susceptible check)		122.3

resistance (see table).

Varieties with large space between tillers because shoots grow obliquely from the base had lower BPH populations;

ARC14766-A had 3 BPH/hill of 2 seedlings. Conversely, varieties with compact tillers had the maximum BPH population. ■

Varietal resistance to rice weevil

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The rice weevil *Sitophilus oryzae* is a

widespread pest of stored grain in the tropics. The pest caused severe damage in the seed store at the Suakoko Experiment Station, where temperature and humidity were not controlled. Some cultivars were consistently more damaged than others in the same storage conditions.

To study varietal differences in rice weevil damage, 500 healthy grains of 18 varieties were infested with 100 insects each under controlled conditions. Damage was recorded as percentage of grains damaged 8-9 weeks after

Varietal differences in damage caused by the rice weevil and hairiness of grain surface. Liberia.

Variety or line	Damage (%)	Grain surface	Weevils (no.) found on 10 panicles before harvest
P14	66.5	Glabrous	—
IRAT10	30.0	”	—
IR937-55-3	31.0	”	—
Juma 1	20.6	”	6
TOS2581	32.1	”	14
TOS4030	25.0	”	—
M4	14.8	Hairy	—
TOS2583	12.1	Glabrous	9
M18	10.0	Hairy	5
IR5	0.6	”	—
Gissi 27	2.0	”	—
Suakoko 8	2.0	”	—
LAC23	0.5	”	—
IR1754-F5B-23	0.7	Glabrous	10
M55	3.9	Hairy	7
IRAT13	2.7	”	8
OS6	1.5	Glabrous	9
63-83	2.4	Hairy	2

infestation. Varietal differences in resistance to the pest were contrasting. P14, IRAT10, IR937-55-3, Juma 1, TOS2581, and TOS4030 were found susceptible; M4, M18, and TOS2583 were moderately susceptible; and IR5, Suakoko 8, Gissi 27, LAC23, M55, OS6, 63-83, IRAT13, and IR1754-F5B-23 were resistant (see table).

Weevils on IR5 and LAC23 were found dead within 2-3 weeks. Seven of the nine resistant varieties had hairy grain surfaces; all susceptible varieties had glabrous grain surfaces; moderately susceptible varieties had either hairy or glabrous grain surfaces.

The resistance mechanism appears to be either morphological or biochemical in nature or both in different varieties.

Pest infestation in the field occurred before harvest. Rice varieties with smooth grain surfaces attracted more weevils than varieties with hairy grain surfaces (see table).

A Hymenopteran parasite and a Heteropteran predator attacked the rice weevil larvae during storage. ■

Assessment of yield losses caused by the earhead-cutting caterpillar *Mythimna separata* Walker

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The earhead-cutting caterpillar *Mythimna separata* (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) is a serious pest of paddy at crop maturity. During the day the pest hides in the dry soil but at night the larvae climb the plant and cut down the rachillae either for food or as a behavioral habit.

Eleven paddy varieties, which are known to be gall midge resistant, were assessed for grain loss by picking up the cut portions of the panicles in three 1- × 1-m² plots (see table). The insect population varied from 12 to 14 larvae/m² at harvest, despite their migration to adjoining unharvested areas. The weight of the cut-down grain in various varieties was assessed against total yield of the fields.